

Recently, three kaurenoid diterpenes were isolated from another *Didymocarpus* sp., *D. oblonga*¹⁰. In continuation of our work on *Didymocarpus* species, we became interested to examine yet another uninvestigated species *D. podocarpa*, growing in the Darjeeling area in West Bengal.

Extraction of the whole plant of *D. podocarpa* with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) led to the isolation of a compound which has been established as 7,8-epoxy-5,6-dehydrokawain (1) previously isolated from *D. aurentiaca*⁹.

(1)

Compound 1, m.p. 125–26°; $[\alpha]_D^{20} \pm 0^\circ$; R, 0.6 (CHCl₃—MeOH, 9.5 : 0.5) and 0.4 (CHCl₃), was crystallised as colourless needles (petroleum ether—benzene) and analysed for C₁₄H₁₂O₄ (*M*⁺ 244). It gave yellow colour with 5% alcoholic KOH solution which disappeared readily on acidification. It did not give any colour with FeCl₃. The ir spectrum (CHCl₃) of compound 1 revealed ν_{\max} 1710, 1626 (α, β -unsaturated six-membered lactone), 820 (an epoxide function), 760 and 740 cm⁻¹ (a monosubstituted benzene ring); and its nmr spectrum (60 MHz) δ 3.83 (3H, 5-OCH₃), 7.33 (5H, s, monosubstituted benzene ring), 6.11 (1H, d, *J* 2Hz, proton of a 2-pyrone ring), 5.5 (1H, d, *J* 2Hz, proton of a 2-pyrone ring), 4.36 (1H, d, *J* 2Hz, methine protons of an epoxide group), 3.83 (1H, d, *J* 2Hz, methine proton of an epoxide group) showed resemblances with those of 7,8-epoxy-5,6-dehydrokawain. The mass spectrum of compound 1 *m/e* 244 (*M*⁺), 216 (*M*⁺—CO), 187 (*m/e* 216—CHO), 138 (C₇H₇O₃—H), 125 (*m/e* 244—C₈H₇O) and 77 (C₆H₅), was in accord with 7,8-epoxy-5,6-dehydrokawain. Finally, the identification of compound 1 was established by direct comparison with an authentic sample of 7,8-epoxy-5,6-dehydrokawain (m.m.p., co-tlc and superimposable ir spectra).

The occurrence of 7,8-epoxy-5,6-dehydrokawain in *D. aurentiaca* and *D. podocarpa* is of chemotaxonomic interest.

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Flavonoid Glycosides from the Leaves of

Taxodium mucronatum

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IN the absence of any record of work on monoflavonoids and their glycosides of *Taxodium mucronatum*, we studied these flavonoids of its leaves, and the isolation and characterisation of kaempferol, quercetin, quercetin-3-*O*- β -D-glucoside and quercetin-3-*O*- β -D-galactoside are presented here. The occurrence of two glycosides with the same aglycone unit in a plant is found rare in nature.

The air-dried leaves of *Taxodium mucronatum* (1 kg) collected from F.R.I., Dehra Dun (U.P.), were successively extracted with petroleum ether, benzene and acetone. The dried acetone extract was treated with hot water. The insoluble portion on column chromatography over silica gel yielded kaempferol and quercetin¹. The water soluble portion was extracted with butanol and the brown residue obtained after concentration was separated by column chromatography followed by preparative paper chromatography into two fractions A and B.

Compound-A: It was crystallised as yellow needle shaped clusters, m.p. 234–36°; gave green colour with FeCl₃; orange-red Shinoda test and a positive Molish test; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 255 and 368 nm, indicating the compound to be a flavonol glycoside. The pmr spectrum of its acetate showed it to be a monoglycoside. On acid hydrolysis it gave quercetin. The sugar was identified as glucose. Permethylation of the glucoside was carried out by Kuhn's method², which on hydrolysis gave quercetin 5,7,3',4'-tetramethyl ether, m.p. 194–96°. With AlCl₃ it showed a bathochromic shift of 62 nm in the long wavelength band, indicating that the

glucose moiety was present at 3-position¹. In the pmr spectrum of the acetate the signals over the range δ 3.9–5.6 accounted for seven protons of the glucosyl residue. One of these a doublet centred at δ 5.14, was assigned to the C₁'-proton. The large coupling constant (J 7.5Hz) due to transaxial coupling with the C₂'-proton indicated the presence of β -configuration. Compound-A was thus characterised as quercetin-3-O- β -D-glucoside.

Compound-B: Pale yellow needles, m.p. 237°, gave positive Shinoda test and Molish test. Acid hydrolysis (6% aqueous HCl) afforded quercetin and D-galactose. The pmr spectrum (60 MHz, DMSO-d₆) of the glycoside, in addition to typical signals for quercetin skeleton, exhibited seven galactosyl protons. Thus it was a monogalactoside. The position of sugar was determined by studying the uv spectral data of the hydrolysed product of the permethylated glycoside using diagnostic shift reagents. A bathochromic shift of 61 nm in band-I absorption with AlCl₃ indicated that the sugar moiety was linked at 3-position¹. Enzymic hydrolysis of the glycoside with almond emulsin gave galactose showing β -linkage⁸. Thus it was characterised as quercetin-3-O- β -D-galactoside.

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Triterpenes from *Hoya parasitica*

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A number of triterpene alcohols, their acetates and cinnamates, anthocyanins, phenolic acids, flavonoids, acylated flavonoids and their glycosides besides β -sitosterol have been reported earlier from various *Hoya species*¹. Literature survey revealed that no work has yet been reported on *Hoya parasitica* (family: Asclepiadaceae) which is a creeper

growing on either of the two host plants, *Polyalthia longifolia* Thw. or *Pithecolobium saman* Benth. The present communication reports the isolation of a 3,4-seco acid of the lupane series besides lupeol and lupeone.

Air-dried, milled stem of *H. parasitica* Wall. growing on *Polyalthia longifolia* collected locally was extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus with light petrol. The residue left after removal of the solvent was taken up in ether and the ethereal solution was extracted with 1% aqueous caustic potash solution. The aqueous alkaline phase on acidification yielded a solid (0.04%) which was crystallised from methanol to give the pure seco-acid, m.p. 208–12°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} +64.4^\circ$ (c 0.132 in CHCl₃). Its homogeneity was checked by tlc. It gave violet colour in the Liebermann–Burchard test.

The ms of the compound recorded the molecular-ion peak at m/z 442 which corresponds to the molecular formula C₃₀H₅₀O₂. Its ir (KBr) and ¹H nmr (CDCl₃, 90 MHz) data revealed the presence of a carboxylic acid group [ν_{\max} 3 600–3 400 and 1 710 cm⁻¹; δ 9.37 (1H, br, exchangeable with D₂O)], an isopropenyl group² [ν_{\max} 1 640 and 882 cm⁻¹; δ 1.73 (3H, s), 4.77 and 4.65 (1H, d each, J 3Hz)], and six additional methyls [δ 1.1 and 1.0 (3H, s each), 0.93–0.77 (12H, ill-resolved)]. The above data clearly revealed that it was a triterpene acid. On treatment with diazomethane it furnished a monomethyl ester (ν_{\max} 1 740 cm⁻¹) as an amorphous solid, having molecular ion peak at m/z 456, commensurate with the molecular formula C₃₁H₅₂O₂. Besides showing peaks at m/z 427 (M -Me)⁺, 399 (M -ⁱPr)⁺, 257, 218, 217, 203 and 189, the ms of the acid recorded two important peaks at m/z 369 (a) and 223 (b) which are typical of 3,4-seco-lupene and -hopene derivatives³. Further, the appearance of two separate signals as (1H, d each) rather than of a (2H), broadened signal around δ 4.7 indicated⁴ that the compound belongs to the lup-20(29)-ene skeleton.

All the above data, considered together, clearly showed that the acid is 3,4-seco-lup-20(29)-en-3- α -oic